

A Study on Mental Health Status of Secondary School Students in Relation to their Academic Anxiety

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Abstract

The present is an endeavor to study the mental health of secondary school students in relation to their academic anxiety. The main objective of the study is to study the mental health of secondary school students in relation to their academic anxiety in interaction with different variables. The variables involved in the study are mental health, academic anxiety, gender, locality and type of school. The population of the study consisted various government and non- government secondary schools of Almora district of Uttarakhand. A sample of 200 students (100 boys & 100 girls) was drawn out of the population for study using simple random sampling. The obtained data were analyzed using Mean, Standard deviation and Two-Way ANOVA. The findings revealed that the joint effect of type of school and academic anxiety level doesn't cause any significant difference in the mental health of secondary school students. The joint effect of locality and academic anxiety level doesn't cause any significant difference in the mental health of secondary school student. However, the joint effect of gender and academic anxiety level causes significant difference in the mental health of secondary school students.

Keywords: Mental Health, Secondary School Students, Academic Anxiety.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the fundamental source of human development. By it the innate powers of human beings are developed, their knowledge and skill are enhanced, their behavior is modified and they become civilized & cultured citizens. This task begin right from the birth .They listen and learn to speak after few months of birth followed by training of eating, walking, sitting and all social conducts. When they attain the age of 3-4 years, they are sent to school for formal education. Formal education is the education that is provided by the formal institutions or training centers. It is structured in terms of learning objectives, academic goals, class timings, and duration of the program of study. The instructions put into operation, the teaching learning methods with the aim of providing understanding of the concepts to the learners and help them achieve their academic goals. Ultimate, aim of the education is all round development of child, emotional, intellectual, mental, moral social, vocational etc. One of the aspects of formal education is the Evaluation process which enables the instructors to assess, whether the objectives of education are achieved or not. In the present education system, academic achievement is measured by grade reports, teacher's observation and self -perception (Mahajan, 2015). In secondary level, a high academic achievement is necessary for the students as it will decide their academic success & future life In order to achieve greater success, 2 students have to taste this cut throat competition, which in turn makes them anxious, stressed, worried and sometimes poor performer, resulting in deterioration of the mental health of students. According to WHO 2022 , "Mental

health is "a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community." If the children are not mentally healthy, they cannot be interested in studies and because of this their attention is not focused in studies and they will not be able to take advantage of teaching [Sharma & Sharma, 2021]. Academic anxiety can either enhance or inhibit academic performance and it depends on how an individual student perceives the academic situation (Mohanto et.al, 2012). Though an acceptable level of academic anxiety is actually a good thing as it keeps the students motivated to accomplish the academic tasks given to them (Neelam, 2013). There is considerable research evidence that some children have biological predispositions to high levels of general anxiety, making them more susceptible to the effects of being evaluated (Huberty, 2008). Repeated difficulties with test-taking or other performances tend to lower self-confidence, which in turn can create conditions for more frequent and intense experiences of academic anxiety. Also, excessive pressure or coercion likely will worsen students' performance, self-esteem, motivation, and ultimately mental health. Therefore, it is required to study mental health of students of secondary school students in relation to their academic anxiety.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

With advancement and globalization of education, students are burdened with great desire of performance pressure, which leaves them in a great lurch & makes them anxious. Academic anxiety arouses several emotional & physical symptoms such as nausea, hesitation, shivering of body parts etc. which are often neglected and not easy to be detected by the parents or teachers. Students are therefore, tend to move towards false/fake relationship, step into drug addiction, isolating themselves, developing suicidal tendencies, etc. to handle that uneasiness and worry. This creates an understanding gap between the students & teachers and children & parents which may lead to several mental health conditions. If these mental health conditions are not addressed on time, the consequences might be very terrifying in the form of mentally and physically ill nation holders. If mental health is prolonged, it may affect overall personality of the students, which is a matter of serious concern. The present study is therefore, undertaken to study the relationship between academic anxiety and mental health of senior secondary school students.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Mental health and academic anxiety are separately and jointly studied by researchers as discussed: **Mahato & Jangir (2012)** revealed that most of the students experience academic anxiety whereas gender was not found to have any impact on the anxiety scores. **Neelam (2013)** states that an acceptable level of academic anxiety is actually a good thing as it keeps the students motivated to accomplish the academic tasks given to them **Deb et.al.(2015)**, in their study discussed that 63.5% of the higher secondary students experience academic stress. Parental pressure for better academic performance was found to be mostly responsible for academic stress, as reported by 66% of the students. The level of mental health of high school students is moderate and there is significant difference between boys and girls, also rural and urban students in their level of mental health, it might be due to the fact that rural areas are naturally calm, quiet and problems are less compared to urban areas as reported by **Joseph (2015)**. **Dawangliani & et.al. (2021)** argues that there exist above average level of Academic Anxiety among secondary school students. **Kaur (2021)** revealed significant negative relationship has been found between mental health and academic anxiety of secondary school students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To compare the mental health of government and non-government secondary school students in relation to their academic anxiety.
2. To compare the mental health of secondary school students belonging to rural and urban area in relation to their academic anxiety.
3. To compare the mental health of secondary school boys & girls in relation to their academic anxiety.

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant difference in mental health of government and non-government secondary school students in relation to their academic anxiety.
2. There is no significant difference in the mental health of secondary school students belonging to rural and urban area in relation to their academic anxiety.
3. There is no significant difference in the mental health of secondary school boys & girls in relation to their academic anxiety.

SAMPLE

In present study, simple random sampling technique has been applied to draw the sample from population. The sample consisted of 200 students (100 boys & 100 girls) of Almora district of Uttarakhand. 100 students were taken from the government school and 100 from non-government school (further classified into 50 urban and 50 rural).

METHODOLOGY

The nature of the present study involves observation, description, analysis and explanation. Thus, the present study is dealing with normative survey method.

TOOLS USED

In the present study, following tools are used to collect the relevant data:

1. **Mental Health Scale** by Dr. Sushma Talsera & Dr. Akhtar Bano
2. **Academic Anxiety Scale for Children** by Sonal Sharma & Dr. Mohd. Shakir
3. **Personal Information Schedule**

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES INVOLVED

The following statistical techniques were employed in testing the hypothesis of the study:

- Mean
- Standard Deviation
- Two-way Analysis of Variance(ANOVA)

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Hypothesis 1: *There is no significant difference in mental health of government and non-government secondary school students in relation to their academic anxiety.*

Table 1
Mean & S.D. of Mental health of government and non-government secondary school students in relation to their Academic anxiety:

Dependent variable	Type of School	Academic Anxiety	N	Mean	S. D.
Mental health	Government	Low	59	165.63	22.63
		Moderate	29	148.48	22.05
		High	12	145.35	24.201
	Non-government	Low	56	156.16	27.06
		Moderate	36	141.03	24.34
		High	8	130.50	22.78

Table 1 shows the mean & SD of mental health of government and non-government secondary school students in relation to their Academic anxiety. Students with low anxiety have the mean value of 165.63 which indicates very good mental health and that of students with moderate anxiety and high anxiety is 148.48 and 145.35 respectively which indicates good mental health. However, those having low academic anxiety have slightly better mental health than those having moderate and high anxiety.

Meanwhile, the mean scores of non-government secondary school students with low anxiety is 156.16 which indicates very good mental health, the mean score of students with moderate anxiety is 141.03 which indicates good mental health and students with high anxiety has a mean score of 130.50 which indicates average mental health. But, students with low academic anxiety have comparatively better mental health than those having moderate anxiety and high academic anxiety.

Table 2
Two-way Analysis of Variance for comparing the Mental health of government and non-government secondary school students in relation to their Academic anxiety:

Source	Df	SS	MS	F-value	Result
Types of school	1	3301.77	3301.77	6.814**	Significant
Anxiety level	2	15857.58	7928.793	16.363**	Significant
Type of school* Anxiety level	2	202.377	101.189	0.209	Insignificant
Error	194	94006.230	484.568		
Total	200	4823208.00			

** → 0.01 level of significance

The above table shows Two-Way ANOVA for comparing mental health of government and non-government secondary school students in relation to their academic anxiety. The first observed F-value at df (1&194) is 6.814, which is greater than table value 6.81 at 0.01 level of significance. This indicates a significant difference in mental health of government and non-government secondary school students. The second observed F-value at df(2&194) is 16.363, which is greater than the table F-value 4.75 at 0.01 level of significance shows a significant difference in mental health of secondary school students having low ,moderate and high academic anxiety. However, third observed f-value with respect to interaction between type of school and anxiety level is 0.209, which is less than table F-value 2.65 at 0.05 level of significance. This value indicates insignificant difference in the mental health of secondary school students when the type of school and anxiety interact. Hence, the null hypothesis is mostly rejected and partly accepted.

Hypothesis 2: *There is no significant difference in the mental health of secondary school students belonging to rural and urban area in relation to their academic anxiety.*

Table 3
Mean & S.D. of Mental health of secondary school students belonging to rural and urban area in relation to their Academic anxiety:

Dependent variable	Locality	Academic Anxiety	N	Mean	S. D.
Mental health	Rural	Low	58	157.19	20.677
		Moderate	31	143.35	18.411
		High	11	132.18	27.059
	Urban	Low	57	164.91	21.572
		Moderate	34	145.26	27.537
		High	9	148.22	17.824

Table 3 shows the mean & SD of mental health of secondary school students who belongs to rural and urban area in relation to their Academic anxiety. Students who belong to rural area with low anxiety have the mean value of 157.19 which indicates very good mental health and that of students with moderate anxiety and high anxiety is 143.35 and 132.18 respectively which indicates good mental

health. However, those having low academic anxiety have slightly better mental health than those having moderate and high anxiety. Meanwhile, the mean scores of secondary school students who belongs to urban area with low anxiety is 164.91 which indicates very good mental health, the mean score of students with moderate and high anxiety is 145.03 & 148.22 respectively which indicates good mental health. But, students with low academic anxiety have slightly better mental health than those having moderate anxiety and high academic anxiety.

Table 4
Two-way Analysis of Variance for comparing the Mental health of secondary school students belonging to rural and urban area in relation to their Academic anxiety:

Source	df	SS	MS	F-value	Result
Locality	1	2208.215	2208.215	4.487*	Significant
Anxiety level	2	15535.658	7767.829	15.783**	Significant
Locality* Anxiety level	2	833.902	416.951	0.847	Insignificant
Error	194	95482.382	492.177		
Total	200	4823208.00			

*0.05 Level of significance & **0.01 Level of significance

The above table shows Two-Way ANOVA for comparing mental health of secondary school students who belong to rural and urban area in relation to their academic anxiety. The first observed F-value at df (1&194) is 4.487, which is greater than table value 3.89 at 0.05 level of significance. This indicates a significant difference in mental health of secondary school students who belong to rural and urban area.

The second observed F-value at df (2&194) is 15.783, which is greater than the table F-value 4.75 at 0.01 level of significance. This shows a significant difference in mental health of secondary school students having low, moderate and high academic anxiety level. However, third observed F-value with respect to interaction between locality and anxiety level is 0.847, which is less than table F-value 2.65 at 0.05 level of significance. This value indicates that the interaction between locality and academic anxiety doesn't cause any significant difference in the mental health of secondary school students. Hence, the null hypothesis is mostly rejected and partly accepted.

Hypothesis 3: *There is no significant difference in the mental health of secondary school boys & girls in relation to their academic anxiety.*

Table 5
Mean & S.D. of Mental health of secondary school boys and girls in relation to their Academic anxiety:

Dependent variable	Gender	Academic Anxiety	N	Mean	S. D.
Mental health	Boys	Low	62	165.00	18.597
		Moderate	31	152.84	24.040
		High	7	119.43	23.086
	Girls	Low	53	156.36	23.580
		Moderate	34	136.62	20.335
		High	13	150.15	17.425

Table 5 shows the mean & SD of mental health of secondary school boys and girls in relation to their Academic anxiety. Boys with low anxiety, moderate anxiety and high anxiety have the mean value of 165.0, 152.84 and 119.43 respectively which indicates very good, good and average mental health respectively. However, those having low academic anxiety have slightly better mental health than those

having moderate and high academic anxiety level. Meanwhile, the mean scores of secondary school students who belongs to urban area with low anxiety is 156.36, the mean score of students with moderate and high anxiety is 136.62 & 150.15 respectively. All these mean scores indicate good mental health. But, students with low academic anxiety have slightly better mental health than those having moderate anxiety. At the same time secondary school girls with high anxiety level have slightly better mental health than those having moderate anxiety level.

Table 4.6
Two-way Analysis of Variance for comparing the mental health of government and non-government secondary school students in relation to their academic anxiety:

Source	df	SS	MS	F-value	Result
Gender	1	108.616	108.616	0.240	Insignificant
Anxiety level	2	17212.039	8606.019	19.008**	Significant
Gender* Anxiety level	2	7918.856	3959.428	8.745**	Significant
Error	194	87833.818	452.752		
Total	200	4823208.00			

**→0.01 level of significance

The above table shows Two-Way ANOVA for comparing mental health of secondary school boys and girls in relation to their academic anxiety. The first observed F-value at df (1&194) is 0.240, which is less than table value 3.89 at 0.05 level of significance. This indicates an insignificant difference in mental health of secondary school boys and girls.

The second observed F-value at df (2& 194) is 19.008, which is greater than the table F-value 4.75 at 0.01 level of significance. This shows a significant difference in mental health of secondary school students having low, moderate and high academic anxiety level. However, third observed F-value with respect to interaction between gender and anxiety level is 8.745, which is greater than table F-value 4.75 at 0.01 level of significance. This value indicates that the joint effect of gender and academic anxiety creates a significant difference in the mental health of secondary school students. Hence, the null hypothesis is mostly rejected and partly accepted.

MAJOR FINDINGS

1. Significant difference has been found in the mental health of government and non-government secondary school students. Significant difference has been found in the mental health of secondary school students having low, moderate and high anxiety. However, the joint effect of type of school and academic anxiety level doesn't cause any significant difference in the mental health of secondary school students.
2. Significant difference has been found in the mental health of secondary school students who belong to rural and urban area. Significant difference has been found in the mental health of secondary school students having low, moderate and high anxiety. However, the joint effect of locality and academic anxiety level doesn't cause any significant difference in the mental health of secondary school students.
3. Insignificant difference has been found in the mental health of secondary school boys and girls. Significant difference has been found in the mental health of secondary school students having low, moderate and high anxiety. However, the joint effect of gender and academic anxiety level causes significant difference in the mental health of secondary school students.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

In the field of education the study plays a very pivotal role and may turn out producing the best of the being, physical, social and emotional. In education, mental health is very important as we are talking about all round development of a child but it is impossible unless due attention is paid towards the

mental health of children. It is disgraceful to state that education which is responsible for making up of a good human being is contributing towards mental illness of students by means of academic anxiety, sometimes by pressurizing the students to get good marks or the other way round. The study may assist the school administrators, policymakers and stakeholders to revise the curriculum contributing in better mental health of the students and appoint counselors in school to address the academic anxiety and mental health issues faced by students. Yoga and meditation can be introduced to children and they must be motivated to practice it regularly in order to perform effectively with joyful and healthy state of mind.

CONCLUSION

The results academic anxiety partially and adversely affects the mental health of students when combined with gender, locality and type of school. However, this effect states a negative impact of present education system which has significantly negative effect on mental health of students and academic anxiety contributes to the mental illness of students. If mental health is not addressed today, we can imagine what we are going to get in return, possibly a mentally-ill nation.

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